

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15665556>

METHOD OF IMPROVING THE TEACHING OF MATHEMATICS IN THE TRAINING OF NON-SPECIALISTS IN HIGHER PROFESSIONAL UNIVERSITIES

Amankulov Husan Gulmurodovich

teacher Branch of the National Research Technological University
MISIS in Dushanbe

Abstract. Meanwhile, the traditional process of teaching deprives students of any interest in learning. This is both a rigid determinism, in which each step of the student in studying a subject is foreseen in advance and determined in time. This is also a refining of the source material - presenting students with selected and simplified information under the guise of the ultimate truth, thereby excluding the demonstration of the most attractive side of any science - the dialectical nature of its development.

Key words. Methodology for improving teaching mathematics in training non-core specialists in higher professional universities.

МЕТОДИКА СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ МАТЕМАТИКИ ПРИ ПОДГОТОВКЕ НЕПРОФИЛЬНЫХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ В ВЫСШИХ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВУЗАХ

Аманкулов Хусан Гулмуродович

преподаватель Филиал Национального исследовательского технологического университета МИСИС в городе Душанбе

Аннотация. Между тем традиционный процесс обучения лишает студентов всякого интереса к учебе. Это и жесткий детерминизм, при котором каждый шаг студента в изучении предмета предусмотрен заранее и определен во времени. Это и рафинирование исходного материала - преподнесение студентам отобранной и упрощенной информации под видом истины в последней инстанции, исключая тем самым показ наиболее привлекательной стороны всякой науки - диалектического характера ее развития.

Ключевые слова. Методика, совершенствования, преподавания математики, при подготовке, непрофильных специалистов, в высших профессиональных вузах.

Our main task is to ensure the formation of a high general and professional culture of the teacher, his readiness for pedagogical creativity. This is evidenced by the practice of teaching in higher education, covered in scientific and methodological literature there is not enough multi-level, mobility, flexibility, continuity, succession, variability.

The problem of establishing an optimal ratio of educational forms of work still remains unresolved; a disproportion between lectures, seminars, laboratory-practical classes and practice at school is still visible. Verbalism is the dominant principle of all training. The gap between the theoretical and practical training of students has not yet been overcome. Many courses taught in specialized disciplines are taught separately from school practice. Questions on Mathematics: axiomatic method; mathematical proofs; elements, sets, relations, mappings, numbers; combinatorics; finite and infinite sets; basic ideas of mathematical analysis; mathematics of randomness; elements of probability theory; the role of mathematics in the humanities.

One of the main features of the modern concept of education is its humanization. The content of this concept is that the personality of the student, the satisfaction of his needs and the development of abilities are at the center of the educational process. Humanization (Latin - humane) presupposes the "humanization" of knowledge, i.e. such an organization of the educational process in which knowledge has a personal meaning, and the student himself "does not lose" his originality in the learning process. Humanization of education is a condition for the harmonious development of the individual and the enrichment of his creative potential.

Meanwhile, the traditional process of teaching deprives students of any interest in learning. This is both a rigid determinism, in which each step of the student in studying a subject is foreseen in advance and determined in time. This is also the refining of the source material - presenting students with selected and simplified information under the guise of the ultimate truth, thereby excluding the demonstration of the most attractive side of any science - the dialectical nature of its development.

The educational system should act as the main source of multiplying the intellectual potential of society, the initiator of solving urgent problems. It goes without saying that the key position in this system is occupied by the teacher, and his professional development and activity constitute a priority direction in the theory and practice of education and upbringing.

At present, what is needed is not just a teacher - a transmitter of knowledge, but a person capable of organizing the active acquisition and assimilation of knowledge and generalized mental actions by students, and developing the creative activity of students. Creativity is not limited to some special "creative" types of activity. The possibilities of creativity are contained in many types of activity, for example, educational and cognitive. Thus, they arrived at a multi-level structure of higher education in Tajikistan, which aims to expand the capabilities of higher education in satisfying the diverse cultural and educational needs of individuals and society, increasing the flexibility of general cultural, scientific and professional training of specialists, taking into account the changing needs of the economy and the labor market.

At present, the Tajik school faces a major problem - solving issues of national education of schoolchildren, including by means of mathematics, relying on the pedagogical views of thinkers of the medieval East. And this is in conditions when the necessary literature and visual aids are absent. Historical material is very scarce: autobiographical data about mathematicians and other historical data related to the development of mathematics as a science. Higher professional universities should provide the opportunity to master the system of scientific knowledge about man and society, history and culture, to receive fundamental natural science training and the basics of professional knowledge in the areas of study. The training of primary school teachers is aimed at producing specialists ready for independent creative professional activity.

Practice shows that a specialist: - is aware of the personal and social significance of his profession; - has a scientific and humanistic worldview; - knows the forms and methods of scientific knowledge and their evolution, is proficient in various ways of

knowing and mastering the surrounding world; understands the role of science in the development of society; - is proficient in modern methods of searching, processing and using information, knows how to interpret and adapt information for the addressee; - is capable of revising his own positions, choosing new forms and methods of work in the context of developing science and changing social practice; - is psychologically and methodologically prepared for work in poly- and interdisciplinary fields of knowledge; - is aware of the intrinsic value of childhood as a special period of human personality development. In the education system, it requires a comprehensive methodological and mathematical preparation of the future teacher. It affects the implementation of continuity and the associated prospects of the student's education. Continuity and prospects represent two sides of the same phenomenon. Consistent implementation of continuity gives the process, the phenomenon a prospective character. A professional teacher must know the level of mental development of the child who came to him after kindergarten (or home education) and have an idea of the level that he should achieve in mathematical education.

The formulation of this question requires the primary school teacher to have a vision of the prospects for teaching mathematics, a deep understanding of the ways in which students acquire knowledge and, in accordance with this, a correct assessment of the students' assimilation of the material with a focus on what requirements will be presented to the preparation of students at the next stage of education.

Based on all of the above, three groups of shortcomings can be identified that reduce the level of professional training of teachers: First, we will note the reasons why the training of future teachers in pedagogical universities does not meet the needs of today's schools: - the absence of textbooks or teaching aids and material resources that meet the requirements of school and university reforms, - the forms and methods of teaching, the organization of independent work of students and its control are insufficiently developed, - insufficient attention to intra- and interdisciplinary connections, - students' understanding of the possibilities of mathematics for the development of the creative personality of primary school students is not sufficiently

developed, - an individual approach to the preparation of students taking into account their personal qualities and interests is not sufficiently implemented, - the knowledge acquired by students is insufficient for the manifestation of creative initiative in future teaching activities. The goals also define the learning outcomes, which are no longer formulated as characteristics of intellectual activity (ability to use thought processes, methods of reasoning, techniques of cognitive activity) that the student must demonstrate when solving certain problems.

The content of mathematical education includes knowledge that does not simply reflect the foundations of science, but also knowledge that makes it possible to realize the goals set, primarily the connections of mathematical knowledge with the sciences, with the arts, practical activities, the surrounding world, and methods of acquiring knowledge. It is also assumed that mathematical information will be expanded, primarily mathematical methods that have both developmental and applied significance.

Thus, the teacher's activity by its very nature is creative; the subject training of students of pedagogical faculties should be aimed at constructing something new - the knowledge itself or methods of acquiring knowledge and highlight the following contradictions: the lack of a personally oriented methodology for teaching mathematics to primary school students and the installation for considering this direction in the content of the methodological training of students; the general educational focus of the preparation of students and the acquisition of practical professional skills; traditional approaches in pedagogical universities and the current needs of the school; work with already constructed content describing the process of teaching mathematics to primary school students, and an increase in activities related to the creation of the learning process (activity component); content-centric and personality-centric ideas; the inertia of the existing training of future teachers and the dynamism of this process, etc.

It follows that teaching mathematics to primary school students should be considered as a complex dynamic system, focused on the individual capabilities of each student, his life and professional abilities, should meet the requirements of fundamentality, continuity

and prospects, connections of mathematical knowledge with the humanities, with the arts, practical activities, the surrounding world, methods of acquiring knowledge. the formation of types of thinking (heuristic, algorithmic, abstract, spatial, creative, etc.) and its qualities, independent deepening and expansion of acquired knowledge; learning outcomes should be considered as characteristics of intellectual activity (ability to use mental operations, methods of reasoning, techniques of cognitive activity).

The content of the analytical stage is the student's presentation of the task in general terms, anticipation of the final result, and determination of the general conditions for achieving this result. The operational stage is characterized by the definition of specific methods of activity leading to the achievement of the final result in solving the problem. Finally, the synthetic stage consists of understanding the work already done, analyzing the actions performed. Since elements of reflection are inherent in each stage of activity, the final synthetic stage of activity seems to merge with the two previous stages.

Literature

1. Amankulov H. G. Modern information technologies for the development of students in the acquisition of knowledge. Proceedings of the XIII scientific and practical conference of young scientists and students with international participation, dedicated to the "Year of Tourism and Folk Crafts Development" Volume 2. 2018. Dushanbe. P. 168
2. Amankulov H. G. Dependence between angles in a regular p-gonal pyramid. "Modern problems of teaching math, physics and computer science in secondary and higher education" Dushanbe, TSPU "Sifat", 2016 c.2016
3. Dzhumaev M. I. Improving Integral Education – An Opportunity to Prepare Future Primary Teachers for Computer Education. SKOPUS. *Journal of Management World* 2025, 2: st.587-599 DOI: 10.53935/jomw.v2024i4.1002.
4. Djumaev M.I. Problems of modern mathematics and its teaching based on the national curriculum of Uzbekistan. I International Scientific And Practical Conference

“Modern Education And Psychology Facing Complex Problems: Synergetic Approach Problems Affecting Personal Development”, APRIL 15, 2025. 121-128 p.

5. M.I Djumaev. Problems of modern mathematics and its teaching in the context of the national curriculum of Uzbekistan. Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference on the topic "Modern Problems of Mathematics and its Teaching", dedicated to the "Twentieth Anniversary of the Study and Development of Natural-Mathematical and Exact Disciplines in the Spheres of Science and Education" (2020-2040) and the 35th Anniversary of State Independence of the Republic of Tajikistan. Bokhtar. (Part 1) May 31, 2025 156-162 p.

6. M. Djumayev Problems of implementing the national curriculum in mathematics in practice and didactic principles of their solutions Collection of materials of the Republican scientific and practical conference on the topic "New theorems of young mathematicians", (May 23-24, 2025) - T.: Science and Innovation, 2025.9-14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15591809>